

Policy brief

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Deatnu watershed Future Vision Workshop

The RecoSal project

The RecoSal project aims to support collaborative governance for the recovery of a diverse Atlantic salmon population complex in the large River Teno catchment (Teno in Finnish, Tana in Norwegian, and Deatnu in Northern Sámi) in the northernmost Fennoscandia. Through the establishment of collaborations aiming towards the formation of a Living Lab user community, the project will connect knowledge production with salmon management, with a special emphasis on the development of population-specific, target-based assessments of genetically diverse salmon populations in a multicultural setting that values Indigenous and Local Knowledge (ILK) and rights. RecoSal will provide transdisciplinary advice for designing and implementing effective and socially robust governance and management practices with the aim of ecological conservation and recovery of depleted biodiversity.

Map illustrating the study area. The Teno River catchment basin is located between Finland and Norway. Source: Hiedanpää, et al. (2020)

View of the Teno River with a rainbow. Photo: Panu Orell

Mountain Vision Workshop (MVW) Methodology

The workshop follows the metaphor of a mountain climb moving through 5 stages:

Future Vision Workshop (FVW)

A series of four co-design workshops will be held during the RecoSal project's implementation, where stakeholders will be informed and engaged, and where the project process will be decided upon in a participatory manner, and visions and outcomes discussed. The aim is the establishment of a permanent and long-term collaboration among actors after the project ends (i.e., a Living Lab).

The first workshop was held in Utsjoki, Finland, in March 2023 (see Bjärstig & Brattland 2024). A second, scoping workshop took place in Karasjok, Norway, in November 2023 (see Bjärstig, Brattland & Rikkonen 2024). The third workshop was held in Utsjoki in October 2024 as part of the International Indigenous Research Symposium, where the RecoSal project participated with several activities. Among these were a river walk-and-talk (see photo) and the Deatnu Future Visions Workshop. This Future Vision Workshop (FVW) was arranged in collaboration with the MARGISTAR Cost Action (CA21125) and thus followed the approach of a Mountain Vision Workshop (MVW; see description of the method and stages above). This is a tool to collect data from local stakeholders in mountainous communities within the EU. The MVW focuses on immersive engagements with rural stakeholders, addressing their visions and fostering real-world solutions and post-marginalization pathways – all in line with the future vision ambition of the RecoSal project.

In total 23 persons, including facilitators, participated in the FVW. Participants were local people both from Norwegian and Finnish side of the Deatnu/Tana/Teno river. The FVW started with an introduction of the MVW methodology, followed by a short icebreaker session introducing all partici-

pants. The original suggestion was to form one Norwegian language group and one Finnish language group to be run in parallel. However, as the two majority languages were Northern Sámi language and Finnish, the groups were split into one Finnish language group (group 1, led by Mikko Jokinen) and one group with Sámi language and Norwegian speakers (group 2, led by Camilla Brattland) to facilitate group discussions. Both groups followed the first four stages of the MVW methodology and the FVW ended with a plenary (the Descent) where all participants gathered to discuss the outputs (with translation service in Finnish, Norwegian and Northern Sámi).

The FVW took place at the Hotel Utsjoki, which was also venue of the Indigenous Salmon Research Symposium. The symposium main organizers were UiT, The Arctic University of Norway (through the Sharing our knowledge project) and the Saami Council. The FVW was a side event of the symposium and participants of the FVW were invited, recognizing local people – Sámi and non-Sámi – that are relevant informants for future visions of salmon management in light of the Tana salmon crisis and the fishing bans that restrict fishing and impede local Sámi culture and traditional livelihood in the area since 2021.

River walk with Research Professor Jaakko Erkinaro, Luke, and Hans Pieski, local fisher and chairman of the Utsjoki fishery cooperative.
Photo: Mikko Jokinen

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Worksheet illustrating the first activity, the Approach, from Group 2. Image creator: Heidi Eriksen, Ohcejohka/Utsjoki

Results

The two FVW groups displayed different approaches regarding what is a preferable future and how to get there (see table 1). Group 1, consisting of people living mostly in the upper and middle part of the river (Utsjoki area), both Sámi and non-Sámi, focused on problems such as how to stimulate the local economy and bring down bureaucratic barriers between Finland (EU-country) and Norway (non-EU). Utsjoki and the Finnish side of the Teno valley was also seen as an area where newcomers are not always welcomed, or where it takes a lot of time to be accepted as a full member of the community. That might hinder the establishment of new businesses and the introduction of fresh ideas. Moreover, fishing and other nature use should be ecologically sound and sustainable.

Group 2, consisting of local people from the lower to the upper part of the river along the riverbanks on both the Finnish and Norwegian side, focused strongly on salmon and indigenous Sámi rights issues. Their message in brief was that Tana salmon management should be based on Sámi traditional knowledge, respect Sámi indigenous rights and be controlled by Sámi communities. Group 2 did not focus on other developments or future issues. One reason might be that they were oriented to talk about salmon issues as a side event of the symposium and were not so thoroughly familiarized with the FVW agenda and MVW methodology.

Table 1. Results and key messages from the two groups at the FVW.

Group	Key message that describes a prosperous future for the Teno valley	An issue that must change	Measures on how to tackle challenges	Statement
Group 1	Nature should be used in an ecological way; cross-cultural conflicts are mitigated and newcomers with their business are welcomed.	Non-acceptance of the place – difficulty for new people and businesses to settle in and propose new things, alienation of the new and the outsider, language and border bureaucracy barriers.	Teach the Norwegian language, remove border barriers, facilitate cross-border cooperation, pilot municipal self-governance.	We want the Tenojoki Valley to be a prosperous and uncontentious area in the future, easy to settle in and start a business. This is important for the vitality of the region and the wellbeing of its people, and it is achieved when there are thriving new businesses and people who feel welcome and at home in the area.
Group 2	River management based on Sámi rights, rule and traditional knowledge.	Becoming free from state and ministerial power to allow Sámi themselves to manage the river. Descendants who have moved away from Sámi areas should also have fishing rights and responsibilities.	Communication – talking and listening to each other – between different Sámi organizations and communities, on both sides of the Deatnu/Tana river region and fjord.	Salmon in the Deatnu/ Tana river is managed based on local and traditional Sámi knowledge, Sámi cultural values and their Indigenous rights.

Summing up – reflections and recommendations

Regarding the format of the FVW, it is always challenging to conduct interactions in several languages simultaneously. There was initially some confusion around language and translation that mostly affected group 2. There were also some technical problems that impeded the possibility to show PowerPoint slides when conducting the activities. Finally, the MVW methodology needs enough time to be implemented in full and not be rushed through due to time limitations. These lessons learned will be brought forth to upcoming MARGISTAR workshops. Despite the above challenges, straightforward and valuable interaction and discussion on the future of the Teno valley and the management of salmon took place among the participants.

When it comes to the recommendations rendered from the FVW, it becomes clear that group 1 had more focus on the needs of economic development, cross-border collaboration and local governance, whereas group 2 emphasized the need for managing salmon on the basis of local, traditional Sámi knowledge. These views do not stand in conflict with one another – rather the opposite – combined they can enforce locally sustainable and viable management of salmon that recognizes ecological, social, cultural, as well as economic aspects. However, to move in that direction the participants of the FVW need to join forces with local politicians, the Sámi parliaments, and researchers to leverage the local needs and perspectives as well as indigenous rights and knowledge into national decision-making regarding salmon management in both Norway and Finland. The possibility of establishing a common forum (traditional knowledge board) with participants from both sides of the river was also raised as another means to reach the common goal, either a yearly forum organized as a consensual meeting (for instance in the form of a lavvo dialogue, see photo) or another model. A process to arrive at this cross-river forum should be established.

MARGISTAR (COST Action 21125) is a forum for knowledge synthesis, exchange, and co-creation that brings together scientists, stakeholders, and policymakers to collaboratively reflect on the challenges for sustainability in mountainous regions while moving progressively towards real-world solutions.

More information about MARGISTAR:
<https://margistar.eu/>

Boats used in traditional salmon fishing now lying ashore waiting for the fishing ban to be lifted. Photo: Jaakko Erkinaro

Further reading and references:

Bjärstig, T., & Brattland, C. (2024). Recovering diversity in salmon populations and cultures of fishing in the subarctic River Teno – stakeholder meeting and kick-off. Policy Brief 2024:2, Department of Political Science, Umeå University. <https://umu.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1901143/FULLTEXT01.pdf>

Bjärstig, T., Brattland, C., & Rikkonen, T. (2024). Scoping Workshop on Collaborative Salmon Research. Policy Brief 2024:3, Department of Political Science, Umeå University. <https://umu.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1901999/FULLTEXT02.pdf>

*Hiedanpää, J., Saijets, J., Jounela, P., Jokinen, M., & Sarkki, S. (2020). Beliefs in conflict: The management of Teno Atlantic salmon in the Sámi Homeland in Finland. *Environmental Management*, 66, 1039-1058.*

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